

Studies of some Organic Salts of Heteropolymolybdates containing two Hetero Atoms

S K ROY^{*a}, RANI JAISWAL^a and K C DEY^b

^aP. G. Department of Chemistry, Ranchi College (Ranchi University), Ranchi-834 007

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Mahila College, Chaibasa

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Mixed heteropoly-oxometallates of molybdenum and their organic salts are of much interest¹. Qureshi *et al.*² reported that Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} can replace molybdenum in 12-molybdosilicic acid to form mixed heteropoly-anions of the type [SiZMo₁₁O₄₀H₂]ⁿ⁻. We have investigated the replacement of molybdenum by vanadium in well characterised³ 12-heteropoly-anion [SiMo₁₂O₄₀]¹²⁻ and prepared the sodium, guanidinium and tetraalkylammonium salts of the resulting new heteropolyanion [SiVMo₁₁O₄₀]⁵⁻. The compound have been characterised by ir, DTA-TGA and molecular weight data.

The sodium salt of 11-molybdovanadosilicic acid has been prepared from molybdosilicic acid. The preparation of the quarternary ammonium salts has also been described. Ir spectra of the compounds have been explained using those of guanidinium carbonate and tetramethyl ammonium chloride as standards. The positions and assignments of the main bands due to different types of metal-oxygen linkages are listed in Table 1.

TABLE I—INFRARED SPECTRA OF THE HETEROPOLY COMPOUNDS
M₅[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀]xH₂O

Comp. I.	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)			
	(Mo-O-Mo) ^a	(Mo-O) ^b	(V-O) ^c	(Si-O) ^d
Na	805m 790s	960s 905m 873m	1048s 992m	490s
C(NH ₂) ₄	810m 780s	932s 890m 850m	1008m 985s	492s
N(CH ₃) ₄	820s 795m	952s 915m 856s	992s 940m	487m
N(C ₂ H ₅) ₄	835s 815m 782m	925s 895m 857m	1075s 975m	498s

^a Ref. 7. ^b Ref. 5. ^c Ref. 6. ^d Refs. 1, 7

The thermal studies of the heteropoly compounds were conducted by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and by heating at fixed temperature, followed by solubility determination. The heating at fixed temperature was performed in a muffle furnace. To ascertain decomposition due to heating, the heated samples (0.5–1.5 g) were placed in water (40 ml) and stirred for 0.5 h for solubility determination. The endotherms found within temperature of 70–350° correspond to the loss of peripheral water or the water of crystallisation, whereas the exothermic peaks in the range of 350–410° denote the loss of water of constitution of the compounds. It was found that dehydrated salts can exist upto 410°, above which complete degradation of heteropoly-anion (irrespective of salts taken) occurred. The chemical analyses of the residual samples indicated the existence of mixed metal oxides. The insolubility of the heated samples at this stage also confirmed the decomposition of heteropoly-salts.

The apparent molecular weight of the sodium salt of the compound, determined cryoscopically taking 0.4 g of Na[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀].14H₂O and using Na₂SO₄.10H₂O–water system as solvent by the literature methods^{8,9}, was found to be 2015 ± 30 against the theoretical heteropoly-anionic weight of 2072.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. The metals present in the compounds were estimated using an ARL 3410 (M/s Applied Research Laboratories, Switzerland) atomic emission spectrophotometer and C, H, N by semimicro-method using a Coleman elemental analyser. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Thermal data were obtained on a NETZSCH simultaneous Thermal Analyzer STA 409 (West Germany) instrument at a heating rate of 5° min⁻¹.

Sodium 11-molybdo-vandosilicate : To freshly prepared³ molybdosilicic acid (17.2 g) dissolved in lukewarm water (50 ml) was added slowly an aqueous solution (15 ml) containing freshly prepared⁸ sodium-metavanadate (1 g) with vigorous stirring maintaining the pH of the solution at 2.5 by using acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. This reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then filtered and left for crystallisation. Bright yellow crystals that separated out was recrystallised from warm water and washed with ethanol followed by ether (Found : Na, 4.9; Si, 1.76; V, 1.9; Mo, 65.6; Na₅[SiVMo₁₁O₄₀].14H₂O calcd. for : Na, 5.2; Si, 1.2; V, 2.3; Mo, 58.8%). The molecular formula was assigned following views and suggestions of Keggin¹⁰ on heteropolyanion [Xⁿ⁺Mo₁₂O₄₀]⁽⁸⁻ⁿ⁾⁻.

Guanidinium, tetramethylammonium and tetraethyl ammonium salts of sodium 11-molybdo-1-vanadosilicate : These were prepared by treating stoichiometric amounts of the concentrated aqueous solution of the compound with guanidinium chloride, tetramethyl ammonium chloride and tetraethyl ammonium chloride solutions respectively. The resulting compounds were crystallised as discussed above. The compounds showed correct analytical results for C and H.

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